

ComeThinkAgain – COMputational and Entrepreneurship THINKing And Green Agenda INnovations

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INTRODUCTION

Digitization and production innovations in combination with the ongoing climate change pose many challenges for our private but also the professional life. Specifically, education systems and the labor market have to address new demands while also facing new challenges, such as defining these skills and implementing teaching methods to acquire them. In this context, the European Commission calls for new skills to keep the EU's labor market competitive [1]. The recently started Erasmus+ project "ComeThinkAgain" (CTA)¹ aims to address these challenges by fostering a strategic collaboration between Higher Education (HE), Vocational Education and Training (VET), enterprises, and research organizations. One of the main outcomes of the project is the development, implementation and evaluation of a cross-sectoral, standardized training and certification system called **CTA-CETS (Certification based Education Training System)** for the three areas ('pillars') of 1) Computational Thinking Skills (CT), 2) Entrepreneurship Education & Innovation Skills (EE) as well as 3) Social Responsibility, Sustainability & Green Skills (GS). ComeThinkAgain is co-funded by the European Union (ERASMUS-EDU-2023-PI-ALL-INNO) and includes project partners from Austria (University of Teacher Education Styria, Austrian Computer Society), Switzerland (University of Teacher Education Zurich), Germany (Gesellschaft für Informatik), Estonia (University of Tartu), Finland (University of Oulu), Denmark (Mercantec), Belgium (The Square Dot Team), Spain (Grupo Inmark) and Ireland (Konnektable Technologies).

¹ <https://comethinkagain.eu/>

PROCESS/WORK PACKAGES

Active teachers, vocational education trainers equip future workers with the necessary skills, therefore a train-the-trainer approach is one of the central methods applied in the project. The CTA-CETS is inspired by the concept of the International Certification of Digital Literacy (ICDL) and relies on well-proven methodologies and concepts such as blended-learning, e-learning, Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), nano-degrees and micro-certifications embedded into a state-of-the-art learning management system (LMS). The project is organized in five highly interrelated operational and supporting work packages (project management, content creation, piloting and evaluation, implementation, dissemination). Data collection for the evaluation is done using a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative measures. Data is analyzed accordingly using descriptive and inferential statistics as well as content analysis and triangulation [2].

MOST RELEVANT RESULTS, CONCLUSION AND ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The project started in Q2 2024 and is currently in its initial stage of setting the ground, performing related research, establishing an External Advisory Board and organizing co-creation workshops with stakeholders. One of the most relevant results of the project is the Certification based Education Training System (ComeThinkAgain-CETS) including curricula and learning material for the three pillars CT, EE and GS in alignment with the three major European reference frameworks, the Digital Competence Framework (DigComp), the Entrepreneurship Competence Framework (EntreComp) as well as the European Sustainability Competence Framework (EntreComp). Pilot implementations and evaluations of CETS with the target group, in collaboration with project-internal but also external HEs and VET providers across five European countries, will ensure high quality, solid validation, and broad acceptance.

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